

Mechanism of Ruthenium(III) Catalysis in Oxidation of Levulinic Acid by *N*-Bromoacetamide in Perchloric Acid

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Manuscript received 14 March 1990, accepted 9 April 1991

Oxidation of levulinic acid to succinic and formic acids by *N*-bromoacetamide (NBA) in perchloric acid media in the presence of mercuric acetate as scavenger and ruthenium(III) chloride as catalyst has been studied. Kinetic data have been used to discuss the mechanistic implication of the oxidation.

N-Bromoacetamide¹ (NBA) is biologically active inhibiting the enzyme action of rennin. Recently, its mode of oxidation in uncatalysed processes^{2,3} has been established, but very little informations⁴ are available about its mode of oxidation in catalysed reactions. This prompted us to report on the mechanism of Ru^{III} catalysis in NBA oxidation of levulinic acid.

Experimental

All chemicals were of AnalaR grade. NBA was prepared by the reported method⁴ and its purity was checked by iodometric method. Ruthenium(III) chloride (Johnson & Matthey) solution was prepared in HCl of known strength. The progress of the reaction was monitored by iodometric estimation of NBA remaining at regular time intervals upto completion of two half-lives of the reaction.

Results and Discussion

The reaction shows zero order kinetics with respect to NBA (Table 1) suggesting its involvement in fast step after rate-determining step. The reaction

was observed to show linear relationship between zero order rate and [Levulinic acid] indicating thus first order with respect to levulinic acid (Fig. 1). First order dependence of the reaction on each, H⁺ ion and Ru^{III} is obvious from the slope values (1.08 and 1.02 for variation of [H⁺] and [Ru^{III}], respectively) of plots between log (-dc/dt) and log [H⁺] or log [Ru^{III}] (Fig. 2). Insignificant effect of ionic strength variation on reaction rate was observed. Successive

Fig. 1. Plot of $-dc/dt$ vs [Levulinic acid]; [NBA]= 1.00×10^{-3} M, [H⁺]= 5.00×10^{-2} M, [Ru^{III}]= 4.82×10^{-6} M, [KCl]= 1.00×10^{-3} M, [Hg(OAc)₂]= 1.25×10^{-3} M, temp=35°.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF NBA AND ACETAMIDE CONCENTRATIONS ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION*

[Levulinic acid]= 2.50×10^{-3} M, [HClO₄]= 2.50×10^{-3} M,
[Ru^{III}]= 4.82×10^{-6} M, [KCl]= 1.00×10^{-3} M,
[Hg(OAc)₂]= 3.34×10^{-3} M, Temp.=35°

[NBA] × 10 ⁴ M	(-dc/dt) × 10 ⁷ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹
4.00	1.90
5.00	1.90
6.67	1.92
8.00	1.94
10.00	1.80
12.50	1.96
16.67	2.06
4.00 ^a	1.92
4.00 ^b	1.88
4.00 ^c	1.94

*[Acetamide]: ^a4.00, ^b6.00, ^c12.50 × 10⁻³ M.

Fig. 2. (A) Plot of log (-dc/dt) vs log [H⁺] at 35°, (B) Plot of log (-dc/dt) vs log [Ru^{III}] at 35°, [NBA]= 1.00×10^{-3} M, [Hg(OAc)₂]= 1.25×10^{-3} M, [Levulinic acid]= 2.50×10^{-3} M, [KCl]= 1.00×10^{-3} M, [Ru^{III}]= 4.82×10^{-6} M (A), [H⁺]= 5.00×10^{-2} M (B).

addition of acetamide (one of the reaction products) did not influence the rate (Table 1). The reaction remains unaffected on changing the concentration of either mercuric acetate or chloride ions.

Thermodynamic parameters ΔE (71.82 ± 0.25 kJ mol⁻¹) and ΔS (14.36 JK⁻¹mol⁻¹) were evaluated from the linear Arrhenius plot in the temperature range 30–50°.

The oxidation of levulinic acid by acidic solution of NBA resulted in the formation of succinic and formic acids, acetamide and HBr,

where, R is CH₂COOH group. The products succinic and formic acids were identified by conventional method⁶.

Bromide ions formed in the reaction interacts with NBA to produce bromine which sets parallel oxidation of levulinic acid. In order to ensure pure NBA oxidation, mercuric acetate was added to scavenge bromide ion^{2,3}.

Probable oxidising species of NBA in acidic media are NBA itself, NBAH⁺, HOBr and (H₂OBr)⁺ (Ref. 2). Zero order in NBA indicates its involvement in fast steps after rate-controlling step. Thus with the present kinetic data, it is not possible to ascertain the exact oxidising species of NBA but it matters little which of the aforesaid species is the real reactive species of NBA as it is involved in fast step. For the sake of convenience, NBA has been taken as reactive species, although any of the four species can be assumed as the real one. Ruthenium(III) chloride has been reported to exist as [RuCl₆]³⁻ in acidic media⁷. The following mechanism is proposed on the basis of the results.

where, R is CH₂COOH group.

Forward reaction is slow and the rate-determining-step,

where, NBH is acetamide.

The rate law derived on the basis of above mechanism is as follows :

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBA}]}{dt} = k_2 K_1 [\text{Levulinic acid}][\text{H}^+][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$$

which is in complete agreement with the kinetic observations.

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